

ELIXIR Commissioned Service [2024-SCIENCE-BFSP, Work Package 6
- BioDiv-FAIR-Checker: Raising FAIRness of European biodiversity data
through ELIXIR-aligned standards, services, and training]

M6.1 Discussion forum for multiple biodiversity communities to express their shared needs

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security & Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

BioDiv-FC improves FAIRness assessment of biodiversity data by extending FAIR-Checker with biodiversity-aware profiles and machine-actionable recommendations. Biodiversity communities generate diverse digital resources, including genome-related sample records, specimen and collection objects, and long-term ecosystem datasets, yet generic FAIR assessment tools often do not reflect the metadata practices, identifier schemes, and reuse constraints that shape these resources in real repositories. BioDiv-FC addresses this gap through a community-led process in WP6 that gathers requirements, harmonises expectations, and supports implementation in FAIR-Checker. This report documents Milestone M6.1 under WP6 Activity 2 and Task T1, defined as the provision of a discussion forum for multiple biodiversity communities to express shared and community-specific FAIR assessment needs. During the first project month, we held structured consultations with iBOL, LifeWatch ERIC, eLTER, DiSSCo, and GGBN, while ERGA requirements were documented through project-team expertise and ongoing operational involvement in ERGA data management. Across communities, we identified accessible objects, metadata expectations, identifier practices, machine-readable access routes, and valid exceptions such as embargoes, sensitive data, and incomplete early-stage records. The meetings show that all target communities provide a workable basis for automated FAIR assessment, while also revealing substantial heterogeneity in metadata models and validation expectations. These outputs have been transferred to Task T2 and will be used by the ELIXIR-FR implementation team, with project partners, to prepare test cases and calibrate FAIR-Checker scoring for FAIR and actionable biodiversity assessments.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DwC	Darwin Core
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
ERGA	European Reference Genome Atlas
GGBN	Global Genome Biodiversity Network
iBOL	International Barcode of Life

Supporting Documents

[BioDivFC Community meetings.pdf](#)

Introduction

Biodiversity research is producing an unprecedented volume and diversity of digital resources, spanning genome assemblies, specimen records and images, and long-term ecosystem datasets. This growth has created major opportunities for data reuse across genomics, ecology, and conservation science, but it has also exposed a persistent methodological gap in how FAIRness is evaluated. Generic FAIR assessment tools such as F-UJI (Anusuriya and Huber 2020) are valuable for broad benchmarking, yet they do not capture the domain-specific metadata expectations, identifier practices, and reuse constraints that shape biodiversity data in real repositories. As a result, well-curated biodiversity resources may receive FAIR evaluations that do not reflect their actual value or readiness for reuse, especially when community norms differ across genomics, specimen, and ecological data types. The BioDiv-FC project addresses this gap by extending the scope of FAIR-Checker (Gaignard et al., 2023) with biodiversity-aware evaluation profiles, machine-actionable recommendations, and implementation pathways that can be adopted by research infrastructures and data providers. Within WP6, this work is organised so that community requirements are first collected and harmonised in Task T1, then translated into machine-actionable metadata profiles and validation rules in Task T2, and later tested and refined through community engagement activities in Task T3. The present report documents Milestone M6.1, defined as a discussion forum for multiple biodiversity communities to express their shared needs. In practice, M6.1 provides the first structured evidence base for BioDiv-FC by capturing what objects should be assessed, which metadata fields are considered minimum or recommended, which identifiers are expected, where machine-readable metadata can be retrieved, and which legitimate exceptions should not be treated as failures. To deliver this milestone, we organised a series of online meetings during the first month of the project with major European biodiversity initiatives and networks, including iBOL, LifeWatch ERIC, eLTER, DiSSCo, and GGBN, while ERGA requirements were documented through direct project-team expertise and ongoing operational involvement of Swiss node members in ERGA data management and project coordination. The aim was to gather community views and to produce implementation-ready inputs for the next project phase. In particular, the outputs summarised in this milestone are intended to support the ELIXIR-FR implementation effort in Task T2 by informing the design of representative test cases and the calibration of FAIR-Checker scoring behaviour across communities. This step is needed to ensure that the tool distinguishes genuine FAIRness gaps from valid constraints or incomplete early-stage records. The following sections summarise the outcomes of these consultations and provide a comparative overview of the requirements identified across communities (Table 1).

Table 1. Summary of community meetings that took place in the first month of the project.

European biodiversity initiative or community	Meeting date
International Barcode of Life - iBOL	02 February 2026
LifeWatch ERIC	04 February 2026
Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research – eLTER	10 February 2026
Distributed System of Scientific Collections – DiSSCo	11 February 2026
Global Genome Biodiversity Network – GGBN	19 February 2026

Progress towards the milestone

This milestone delivers the activities carried out in WP6 Activity 2 (Task T1), by documenting the outcomes of structured consultations with the target biodiversity communities. The scope of these consultations was to collect information that can support the harmonisation of minimal and recommended metadata expectations in T1 and their later translation into machine-actionable FAIR-Checker profiles in Task T2, followed by community testing and refinement in Task T3. To provide comparability across communities, each meeting was structured around five shared questions (Table 2) addressing the object to assess, metadata expectations, identifier practices, use of controlled terms, and availability of machine-readable metadata. The resulting synthesis provides the evidence base for biodiversity-aware FAIR assessment rules.

This comparative requirements-gathering exercise constitutes the operational output of WP6 Activity 2 Task T1 for Milestone M6.1, and it provides the evidence needed for the next implementation phase of BioDiv-FC. In order to develop a shared baseline that is scientifically grounded and directly usable in the development of FAIR-Checker, the project team has documented, for each community, the target object for assessment, metadata expectations, identifier practices, controlled terminology, machine-readable access routes, and valid exceptions that should not be considered failures. These results have been transferred to Task T2, where the ELIXIR-FR implementation team, working with project partners, will use them to define representative test cases and tune community-specific validation rules and scoring behaviour so that FAIR assessments remain fair, informative, and useful across genomics, specimen, and ecological data contexts.

Table 2. Summary of the community's answer to each of the five questions. A green key reflects a positive answer from the community, whereas an orange key a partially positive answer.

ERGA	iBOL	LifeWatch ERIC	eLTER	DiSSCo	GGBN
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Do you have an object to assess?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Do you have minimum, recommended, and optional metadata?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Do you have a unique identifier?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Do you have controlled terms	!	!	✓	!	!	✓
Are the metadata in a machine-readable format?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

1. Do you have an object to assess?

ERGA: For ERGA, the object to assess is the sample record (**Table 3**), operationally handled as a BioSample record linked to the sequencing workflow. In practice, the assessment can start from an ENA sample accession or from the corresponding BioSamples record, since BioSamples provides the sample-level metadata used to describe the biological material underpinning genome sequencing submissions.

iBOL: For iBOL, the object to assess is the BOLD DNA barcode record (**Table 3**) represented in the Barcode Core Data Model (BCDM). This is the most appropriate record-level unit for FAIR assessment because it combines specimen, sequence, and associated metadata in a consistent structure, and BOLD exposes these records through the public portal and machine-readable exports.

LifeWatch ERIC: For LifeWatch ERIC, the object to assess should be defined as the dataset metadata record in the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue (**Table 3**), rather than the dataset file itself. The catalogue serves as the entry point for detailed metadata inspection, and dataset records can also be queried programmatically through the catalogue API.

eLTER: For eLTER, the object to assess is the dataset record in the eLTER Digital Asset Register (DAR) (**Table 3**), which functions as the public catalogue for eLTER digital assets and datasets. This is the appropriate entry point for FAIR assessment at this stage because the DAR exposes dataset records and provides an API for record retrieval.

DiSSCo: For DiSSCo, the primary object to assess should be the Digital Specimen (openDS and/or ods:DigitalSpecimen) (**Table 3**), using its DOI PID as the stable entry point. Media and annotations are also DiSSCo digital objects and remain in scope for later extension, but starting with Digital Specimens is more precise for the present milestone and is consistent with the way DiSSCo documents object types and required terms.

GGBN: For GGBN, the object to assess is best described as the GGBN material entity record resolved through a GGBN stable identifier (ggbnId) (**Table 3**), with each identifier leading to a dedicated landing page and RDF representation. In other words, the identifier is the entry point, while the assessed object is the material entity record that the identifier resolves to.

2. Do you have minimum, recommended, and optional metadata?

ERGA: For ERGA, metadata requirements are operationalised through ENA sample checklists, in particular ERC000011¹ and ERC000053² (Tree of Life checklist), which the team uses as the basis to distinguish minimum and recommended expectations for FAIR-Checker rule design.

iBOL: For iBOL, the BCDM provides a structured field set, and the community confirmed that metadata expectations are differentiated in practice between fields needed for baseline reuse and fields that are recommended and should not always trigger failure when absent.

LifeWatch ERIC: For LifeWatch ERIC, dataset metadata records follow a LifeWatch ERIC application profile based on EML2.2.0, and the schema includes 77 attributes, with mandatory versus optional distinctions handled in the catalogue editor and profile documentation.

eLTER: For eLTER, the Digital Asset Register (DAR) dataset profile distinguishes required and non-required metadata elements, with the community consultation clarifying that the present implementation is used as a generic profile across domains and that BioDiv-FC should treat required fields separately from recommended ones.

¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERC000011>

² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERC000053>

DiSSCo: For DiSSCo, there is a defined minimum metadata set for a valid Open Digital Specimen, with required classes and required terms documented in the Digital Specimen quick reference and suited to machine-actionable validation

GGBN: For GGBN, providers publish through Darwin Core Archive or ABCD with GGBN extensions, and GGBN explicitly documents mandatory and recommended fields for data sharing, which is exactly the distinction needed for FAIR-Checker scoring profiles.

3. Do you have a unique identifier?

ERGA: For ERGA, the unique identifier for the object under assessment is the BioSample accession, which may be used directly as an accession string or as the resolvable BioSamples page URL.

iBOL: For iBOL, the primary record identifier is the BOLD Process ID, which links specimen and barcode information at the record level, while Sample ID and BIN identifiers are additional identifiers used for specimen and sequence cluster linkage.

LifeWatch ERIC: For LifeWatch ERIC, the dataset metadata record includes an automatically generated UUID as the resolvable catalogue identifier, and a DOI is strongly recommended where available for the underlying dataset.

eLTER: For eLTER, datasets are typically identified by DOI at the dataset level, although the consultation correctly notes that not every dataset may yet have a DOI.

DiSSCo: For DiSSCo, digital objects are identified by DOI PIDs, with this expectation documented for Digital Specimens and Digital Media and used across DiSSCo object linking.

GGBN: For GGBN, the unique identifier is the GGBN stable identifier URL assigned to the object, which resolves to a landing page and supports links to related resources, including sequence records in ENA where available.

4. Do you have controlled terms?

ERGA: In the ERGA workflow, metadata are constrained through ENA checklist fields, and the community discussion made clear that some fields are expected to follow checklist-defined value conventions and controlled entries where specified.

iBOL: For iBOL, yes, controlled terms are used for selected BCDM fields, including marker-related and other categorical fields, and FAIR-Checker should validate these as

controlled values when present, while avoiding overly strict failure logic for valid incomplete public records.

LifeWatch ERIC: LifeWatch ERIC Application Profiles for dataset metadata records are based on EML2.2.0 and ISO19139. Some metadata fields are controlled lists coming from enumerated lists (e.g., unit), controlled vocabularies, etc., that follow the EML standard. Some fields include the semantic annotation to be put in the form of URIs that are resolvable to controlled vocabularies that provide the corresponding definition and relationships to other terms.

eLTER: For eLTER, the consultation indicates that the DAR currently uses a generic metadata profile and does not yet rely on a broad domain-specific controlled vocabulary layer in the way LifeWatch does, so it is reasonable to say that controlled terms are not a defining feature of the present eLTER profile used for this milestone.

DiSSCo: For DiSSCo, alignment with Darwin Core is a clear direction and controlled vocabularies are being developed and expanded, so to describe this as an ongoing effort is appropriate.

GGBN: GGBN explicitly describes its Data Standard as a set of terms and controlled vocabularies that extend ABCD or Darwin Core for sample-focused use cases, and the FAIR-Checker profile should treat these terms as part of the community rule set.

5. Are the metadata in a machine-readable format?

ERGA: For ERGA, metadata for the BioSample object are available in machine-readable form through EMBL-EBI BioSamples, including Bioschemas JSON-LD on sample pages, which is suitable for automated harvesting by FAIR-Checker.

iBOL: For iBOL, metadata can be retrieved programmatically through BOLD public web services and related programmatic interfaces, including JSON outputs used in BCDM-based workflows.

LifeWatch ERIC: For LifeWatch ERIC, metadata are available both through the user interface and through APIs, with catalogue records retrievable in machine-readable JSON through the API and additional downloadable serialisations provided through the catalogue interface.

eLTER: For eLTER, metadata are retrievable through the DAR API in machine-readable JSON, and the consultation notes can continue to mention JSON-LD support if this reflects the agreed implementation pathway for the BioDiv-FC integration.

DiSSCo: For DiSSCo, metadata are retrievable through the DiSSCo APIs in machine-readable JSON, but JSON-LD is not yet available (although under consideration), which could be an implementation caveat for the project.

GGBN: For GGBN, metadata are available in RDF from the stable identifier landing pages, but JSON-LD is not available, which could be an implementation caveat for the project.

Table 1. Summary of the meetings we had with Data managers and IT from the communities/infrastructure.

Table 3. Summary of the community meetings.

Label in our meetings	What it is (role)	Where the assessable digital object lives	Primary object we FAIR-check (first iteration)	Typical stable identifier/entry point	Example entry as baseline
ERGA	Community/initiative (requirements, practices, exemplars)	ENA / BioSamples (infrastructure)	Sample record underpinning sequencing (BioSamples JSON-LD; ENA/BioSamples accession)	ENA sample accession or BioSample accession; BioSamples .ldjson endpoint	SAMEA112797446
iBOL / BOLD	Community + platform (acts as both)	BOLD portal + APIs	BOLD barcode record (BCDM); optionally dataset/package level	Process ID record page; dataset recordset; DOI 10.5883/DP-Latest	Single record: http://boldsystems.org/record/CHOLH011-12 Dataset: https://doi.org/10.5883/DP-Latest
LifeWatch ERIC	Research infrastructure	LifeWatch Metadata Catalogue (GeoNetwork) + APIs	Dataset metadata record (LifeWatch application profile based on EML/ISO)	Catalogue UUID; record JSON/XML via API	https://metadatacatalogue.lifewatch.eu/srv/eng/catalogsearch#/metadata/dc512697-ed50-40c5-a3cd-1774000444b9
eLTER	Research infrastructure/network	eLTER DAR portal + APIs	Dataset record in DAR	DOI where present; DAR API record	https://doi.org/10.82159/gt66-zt98

DiSSCo	Research infrastructure	DiSSCo services/APIs (openDS)	Digital Specimen (and linked Digital Media / Annotation as feasible)	DOI PID (e.g., dcterms:identifier); DiSSCo APIs	https://doi.org/10.3535/ZVR-CRA-1Y1?no_redirect
GGBN	Community network + aggregation ecosystem	GGBN provider endpoints (DwC-A/ABC D/API depending on provider)	<i>To be agreed</i> (likely sample/specimen record or dataset export)	<i>To be confirmed</i> per provider (portal/PID/DwC-A/ABCD)	

Impact and future work

The consultations reported in this milestone show that the participating communities already provide the core elements needed for biodiversity-aware FAIR assessment, including a defined object for assessment, stable identifiers, and machine-readable metadata access. At the same time, they also showed substantial variation in metadata models, field requirements, and accepted data-sharing constraints across genomics, specimen, and ecological data contexts. This diversity is not a limitation of communities, but a defining feature of biodiversity data practice. It confirms the need for FAIR-Checker profiles that reflect community standards and workflows, rather than applying a single generic interpretation that may undervalue well-curated resources. The immediate impact of M6.1 is therefore methodological and operational within WP6. The information gathered through these community discussions has been communicated to Task T2 and will be used by the ELIXIR-FR implementation team, in collaboration with project partners, to build representative test sets and refine community-specific validation rules in FAIR-Checker. This next phase will use the examples and requirements collected here (see **Table 3**) to tune scoring behaviour and rule severity so that FAIR-Checker can distinguish genuine FAIRness gaps from valid constraints and incomplete records that are acceptable at an early workflow stage. In this way, the project moves from requirements elicitation to implementation on a shared evidence base developed with the participating infrastructures and networks. Looking ahead, we expect the implementation of the requirements captured in this milestone within FAIR-Checker to be completed by June 2026, after which co-creation workshops will be organised with the University of Manchester and the participating communities to test the tool on representative records and datasets. These workshops will provide structured feedback on rule behaviour, false positives, and missing checks, and this feedback will be used to improve the tool before broader release. During this phase, particular attention will be given to cases involving threatened species, restricted access, and partial metadata so that the resulting assessments remain fair and informative in sensitive biodiversity contexts.

Beyond implementation, the outputs of this work will support training and uptake across the ELIXIR and biodiversity data ecosystems. The community feedback gathered during testing will inform training materials for researchers and data stewards, to support the routine use of FAIR-Checker as a practical FAIRness assessment service for biodiversity data. By combining community knowledge, infrastructure practice, and machine-actionable validation, BioDiv-FC can help make FAIR assessment more transparent, more actionable, and more trusted across biodiversity research and data management.

References

Anusuriya Devaraju, & Robert Huber. (2020). F-UJI - An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6361400>.

Gaignard, A., Rosnet, T., de Lamotte, F., Lefort, V., & Devignes, M. (2023). FAIR-Checker: supporting digital resource findability and reuse with Knowledge Graphs and Semantic Web standards. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-023-00289-5>